

Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial study of 1-arylamido-3-chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetidin-2-ones

Spruha A. Gharad* and Baliram N. Berad

Post Graduate Teaching Department of Chemistry, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University,
Nagpur-440 033, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : spruhagharad@gmail.com, bnberad@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 28 April 2015, revised 20 May 2015, accepted 22 May 2015

Abstract : A series of quinoline based β -lactams (azetidinones) have been synthesized via cycloaddition reaction (Staudinger reaction) of imines with ketene. The methodology involves [2+2] cycloaddition of Schiff bases with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine to yield the corresponding 1-arylamido-3-chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetidin-2-ones. The intermediate Schiff bases were synthesized by condensation of 2-chloroquinolin-3-carbaldehyde with various aroyl hydrazides in ethanol. The structures of final compounds have been confirmed on the basis of IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and mass spectral data. The synthesized compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria by broth dilution method. Most of the compounds exhibited good to moderate activity against tested bacteria.

Keywords : β -Lactam, azetidin-2-one, 2-chloroquinolin-3-carbaldehyde, Broth dilution method.

Introduction

Quinoline is a heterocyclic scaffold of paramount importance to human race. Quinoline derivatives are very important class of compounds because of their wide occurrence in natural products¹ and biologically active compounds². The quinoline skeleton is often used for the design of many synthetic compounds with diverse pharmacological properties such as antimalarial³, anti-inflammatory⁴, antibacterial⁵, antifungal⁶, antidepressant⁷, antitumour⁸, neuroleptic activity, antihypertensive and bronchodilator activities.

Azetidin-2-one (β -lactam) ring is present in several widely used families of antibiotics such as penicillins, cephalosporins and carbapenams. The β -lactam antibiotics have been used for many years with limited or no toxicity. Azetidinones are known to exhibit antibacterial⁹, anti-tubercular¹⁰, antifungal, anticonvulsant¹¹, anticancer¹², antiinflammatory¹³, and CNS depressant activity. They also function as enzyme inhibitors and are effective on the central nervous system¹⁴⁻¹⁶. 1,3,4-Trisubstituted β -lactams were found to be potent cholesterol absorption inhibitors¹⁷ and thrombin inhibitors¹⁸.

In view of the potential biological activity of quinoline and azetidinones, it was thought worthwhile to synthesize the title compounds by incorporating both these moieties in one framework.

Results and discussion

Various methods have been developed for the synthesis of functionalized quinolines, the Vilsmeier approach is found to be most efficient¹⁹. The starting compound 2-chloroquinolin-3-carbaldehyde (**2**) was synthesized by earlier reported method²⁰. 2-Chloroquinolin-3-carbaldehyde (**2**) was reacted with various acid hydrazides²¹ (**1a-i**) to obtain corresponding Schiff base derivatives (**3a-i**).

Cycloaddition (Staudinger reaction) is the most simple and efficient method for the synthesis of β -lactams from imines and acid chlorides in presence of mild base²². The substituted Schiff base derivatives (**3a-i**) reacted with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine in 1,4-dioxane to obtain 1-arylamido-3-chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetidin-2-ones (**4a-i**). The overall reaction is schematically represented in Scheme 1. The physical characterization data of compounds (**4a-i**) are tabulated in Table 1.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1-arylamido-3-chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetidin-2-ones (**4a-i**).

Table 1. Physical characterization data of 1-arylamido-3-chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetidin-2-ones (**4a-i**)

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	R _f value ^a
4a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	65	216	0.65
4b	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₂	72	208	0.75
4c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₂	68	210	0.78
4d	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄	70	195	0.60
4e	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₃	64	198	0.74
4f	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	62	201	0.69
4g	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	66	212	0.64
4h	4-C ₅ H ₄ N	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂	70	220	0.68
4i	CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	62	210	0.62

^aSolvent system – ethyl acetate : petroleum ether (2 : 8).

In IR spectra of compounds (**4a-i**), bands corresponding to -C=O functional group were observed at 1682–1700 cm⁻¹ which confirmed the formation of azetidinone ring. The bands corresponding to C-N stretching vibration were observed in the range 1335–1372 cm⁻¹. Chlorine functional group of lactam ring and quinoline ring exhibited peaks at 749–756 and 771–785 cm⁻¹ respectively. In ¹H NMR spectra of compounds (**4a-i**), doublets were observed at 4.49–4.56 ppm and 4.61–4.69 ppm due to the presence of CH-Cl and CH-N proton on azetidinone ring respectively. The aromatic protons resonated in the range 7.30–8.30 ppm and NH proton resonated at 8.15–8.36 ppm. The signals obtained from ¹³C NMR spectra of compounds further confirmed the presence of carbonyl carbon of β-lactam which resonated at 159.26–163.72

ppm. The carbonyl carbon of -CONH linkage resonated in the range 169.70–172.45 ppm. The range between 60.59–63.25 ppm showed the presence of C-Cl group of azetidinone ring while 67.37–69.38 ppm range showed the CH-N linkage of azetidinone ring. The mass spectra of final compounds showed [M+H]⁺ peaks which were consistent with the assigned structure.

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity was carried out by broth dilution method^{23,24}. The newly synthesized compounds (**4a-f**) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* at concentrations 1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5 μg/mL. The discussion and comparison of antibacterial activity with respect to stan-

dard drug Gentamycin was described in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of antibacterial screening of the compounds (**4a-f**)

Compd.	Minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/mL			
	Gram-ve bacteria		Gram + ve bacteria	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
4a	500	1000	500	> 1000
4b	250	500	250	500
4c	250	1000	500	1000
4d	62.5	125	125	250
4e	250	500	250	1000
4f	125	250	250	500
Gentamycin	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5

In present protocol, 500 µg/mL - weakly active, 250 µg/mL - moderately active, 125 µg/mL - good active, 62.5 µg/mL - excellent active.

From the screening results, it has been observed that compounds **4b**, **4c** and **4e** were considered to be moderately active against *E. coli*. Compound **4f** was found to be good active while compound **4d** was found to be excellent active against *E. coli*. Compound **4f** showed moderate activity and compound **4d** showed good activity against *P. aeruginosa*. Compound **4b**, **4e** and **4f** were found to show moderate activity and compound **4d** exhibited good activity against *S. aureus*. Compound **4d** exhibited moderate activity against *B. subtilis*. The remaining compounds of the entire series were found to possess insignificant antibacterial activity.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All melting points were uncorrected and measured using an electro-thermal apparatus. FT-IR spectra were recorded using KBr disk on Perkin-Elmer FT-IR KBr spectrophotometer as thin films with ν_{\max} in inverse centimeter. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were taken on Bruker Avance II 400 NMR spectrometer using CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ as solvent and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard and chemical shifts being reported in parts per million (δ) relative to TMS. Mass spectra were obtained using electron impact (EI) at an ionizing potential of 70 eV. Purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography which was performed on aluminium sheet Silica Gel 60 F₂₅₄ (Merck). The spots were visualized by exposure to UV light and iodine vapours.

Synthesis of (Z)-N'-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-aroylhydrazide (**3a-i**) :

A mixture of 2-chloroquinolin-3-carbaldehyde (**2**) (0.01 mol) and acid hydrazide (**1a-i**) (0.01 mol) containing a catalytic amount of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 3 h in ethanol. The solid that separated out was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol to afford compound (**3a-i**).

(Z)-2-Chloro-N'-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-benzohydrazide (**3b**) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 244 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 776 (C-Cl), 1637 (C=N), 1651 (C=O), 3260 (N-H).

Synthesis of 1-(arylamido)-3-chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetidin-2-one (**4a-i**) :

A mixture of compound (**3a-i**) (0.005 mol) and triethylamine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane and stirred for half an hour. To this well stirred solution, a cold solution of chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) was added slowly at 0 °C. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 1 h and then refluxed for 10 h. The precipitated triethylammonium chloride was filtered off, the filtrate was concentrated to half of its initial volume and then poured onto crushed ice. The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol.

3-Chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-phenylamido-azetidin-2-one (**4a**) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 751, 776 (C-Cl), 1372 (C-N), 1625 (CONH), 1696 (C=O of lactam ring); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 4.52 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.64 (1H, d, *J* 13.2 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 7.30–7.56 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.58–8.10 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.15 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ (ppm) : 61.78, 67.37 (CH of lactam ring), 119.22–146.78 (Ar-C) 149.51 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 162.57, 172.23 (C=O); MS : *m/z* = 386 [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-1-(2-chlorophenylamido)-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetidin-2-one (**4b**) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 756, 785 (C-Cl), 1335 (C-N), 1617 (CONH), 1684 (C=O of lactam ring); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 4.54 (1H, d, *J* 14.0 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.66 (1H, d, *J* 14.0 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 7.32–7.53 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.59–8.06 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.22 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ (ppm) : 62.43, 67.93 (CH of lactam ring),

121.97–147.48 (Ar-C), 147.60 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 163.05, 171.03 (C=O); MS : $m/z = 420$ [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-1-(4-chlorophenylamido)-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-azetid-2-one (4c) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 754, 780 (C-Cl), 1354 (C-N), 1595 (CONH), 1682 (C=O of lactam ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 4.50 (1H, d, J 13.7 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.62 (1H, d, J 13.7 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 7.41–7.46 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.58–8.06 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.18 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 61.22, 68.18 (CH of lactam ring), 119.91–145.31 (Ar-C), 148.78 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 162.71, 171.95 (C=O); MS : $m/z = 420$ [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenylamido)-azetid-2-one (4d) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 755, 782 (C-Cl), 1346 (C-N), 1619 (CONH), 1686 (C=O of lactam ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 4.52 (1H, d, J 13.7 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.63 (1H, d, J 13.6 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 7.38–7.84 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.85–8.30 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.32 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 60.59, 68.35 (CH of lactam ring), 122.81–145.96 (Ar-C), 147.88 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 159.26, 170.14 (C=O); MS : $m/z = 431$ [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenylamido)-azetid-2-one (4e) : IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 753, 779 (C-Cl), 1361 (C-N), 1608 (CONH), 1697 (C=O of lactam ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 4.56 (1H, d, J 12.4 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.69 (1H, d, J 14.4 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 5.09 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 7.41–7.77 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.80–8.28 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.36 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 61.23, 69.07 (CH of lactam ring), 118.75–148.18 (Ar-C), 148.31 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 163.39, 169.70 (C=O); MS : $m/z = 402$ [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-(phenylacetamido)-azetid-2-one (4f) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 749, 771 (C-Cl), 1345 (C-N), 1622 (CONH), 1689 (C=O of lactam ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.56 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.50 (1H, d, J 12.0 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.61 (1H, d, J

14.2 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 7.35–7.74 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.76–8.12 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.17 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 51 (CH₂), 60.77, 67.58 (CH of lactam ring), 120.51–146.26 (Ar-C), 148.95 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 161.35, 170.88 (C=O); MS : $m/z = 400$ [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-methylphenylamido)-azetid-2-one (4g) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 755, 780 (C-Cl), 1346 (C-N), 1616 (CONH), 1690 (C=O of lactam ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.33 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.53 (1H, d, J 13.2 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.63 (1H, d, J 13.6 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 7.32–7.72 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.75–8.15 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.19 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 24.8 (CH₃), 61.80, 68.54 (CH of lactam ring), 121.23–147.81 (Ar-C), 148.46 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 159.87, 172.45 (C=O), MS : $m/z = 400$ [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-pyridylamido)-azetid-2-one (4h) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 752, 783 (C-Cl), 1369 (C-N), 1629 (CONH), 1700 (C=O of lactam ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 4.52 (1H, d, J 13.8 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.63 (1H, d, J 13.8 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 7.38–7.74 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.78–8.30 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.36 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 63.25, 69.38 (CH of lactam ring), 120.61–148.09 (Ar-C), 148.22 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 163.72, 169.82 (C=O), MS : $m/z = 387$ [M+H]⁺.

3-Chloro-4-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-(styrylamido)-azetid-2-one (4i) :

IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 750, 773 (C-Cl), 1338 (C-N), 1610 (CONH), 1689 (C=O of lactam ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 4.49 (1H, d, J 12.0 Hz, CH-Cl of lactam ring), 4.62 (1H, d, J 14.0 Hz, CH-N of lactam ring), 6.90–7.22 (2H, m, CH=CH), 7.31–7.71 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.76–8.18 (5H, m, Qu-H), 8.21 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm) : 61.33, 67.85 (CH of lactam ring), 119.20–147.72 (Ar-C, C=C), 148.50 (C-Cl of quinoline ring), 160.54, 170.21 (C=O); MS : $m/z = 412$ [M+H]⁺.

Procedure for antibacterial screening :

The media used for antibacterial analysis were peptone-10 g, NaCl-10 g and yeast extract 5 g, in 1000 ml of distilled water. Initially, the stock cultures of bacteria were revived by inoculating in broth media and grown at 37 °C for 18 h. The tubes containing above media were autoclaved and added with respective concentrations of samples. Each tube was inoculated with 18 h old cultures (25 µL, 10⁻⁴ cfu). A control tube without samples was inoculated and a tube with only media was maintained as blank. The tubes with Gentamycin were also prepared. All the tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h on a shaker at 140 rpm, and the growth of bacteria were noted at 600 nm. The growth in control tubes were measured against media blank where as the tubes with samples were read against media with compounds at respective concentrations, as blank.

Conclusion

In this paper, a simple and highly reliable method has been devised for the synthesis of a biologically promising scaffold containing β-lactam and quinoline moieties in a single framework. The methodology is based on the Staudinger reaction between a ketene and different substituted imines. Among all the synthesized compounds, compounds (**4a-f**) were screened for their antibacterial activity against four strains of bacteria (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*). The results of antibacterial screening revealed that most of the compounds showed good to moderate activity against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* while less activity against *B. subtilis*. The MIC values of antibacterial screening predicted that compound **4d** exhibited better activity as compared to the other synthesized compounds.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Professor H. D. Juneja, Head, Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur for providing laboratory facilities. Authors are also thankful to SAIF, Chandigarh for spectral analysis and Biogenics, Hubli for antibacterial analysis.

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